

Metadata for publication	Children's selection of emojis to express food-elicited emotions in varied eating contexts
Acknowledgement	This project was conducted as part of the project "Edulia-Bringing down barriers to children's healthy eating", which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 764985.
Publication	The article is published online 08.04.20, with an embargo period of 12 months, and the DOI https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2020.103953
Metadata for data access	Data to this article can be found online at https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2020.103953
Data summary	Data about 1) emoji selection of 7 contexts 2) survey about emoji usage and test evaluation.
Naming	The data file is saved as Data_Emoji selection
Type of data	The data consists of quantitative and qualitative data about 1) children's selection of emojis to express food-elicited emotions in 7 eating contexts (CATA) 2) survey about emoji usage and test evaluation saved in Excel.
For data that is not completely anonymized, briefly describe (1) if and where it is registered that the data contains personal data, and (2) whether and how a Privacy Impact Assessment (PIA) was conducted	No data made available.
Software used for analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • XLSTAT (Version XLSTAT 2018.7, Excel 14.0.6024, Windows 10, Build 54971, XLSTAT-Sensory) • For qualitative data: T-LAB 2020.1 (Plus version 5.1.0.4; T-LAB di Lancia Franco, Italy)
For raw data in physical form (paper-pencil survey, etc.) please specify where this is stored and for how long this will be the case	The publication does not contain raw data in physical form.